

**ASSESSMENT OF THE INFLUENCE OF LEADERSHIP
MANAGEMENT AND SUCCESS OF THE GIRINKA PROGRAM
IN RWERU AND GASHORA SECTORS, BUGESERA DISTRICT,
RWANDA**

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Abstract:

Girinka (the "one cow per poor family" program) is encouraged as a strategy in Rwanda to reduce poverty, specifically where resource-poor farmers get a cow aimed at developing skills and accumulating assets for livelihood improvement as well as the promotion of improved soil fertility about manure use. The study assessed the influence of leadership management on the success of the Girinka Program in Rwanda: a case study of Rweru and Gashora Sectors, Bugesera District. The target population was 41 people while universal sampling technique was used to select all 41 respondents as a sample size. Questionnaire were data collection instrument. The coefficient of determination and regression analysis model were methods of data analysis. Findings revealed that there is a positive and strong correlation between authority and follow up of leaders in leadership management and success of Girinka program as Pearson correlation is .747**; positive and very strong correlation between power and control of leaders and success of the Girinka Program as Pearson correlation is .910** with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the standard significance level of 0.01. The results show that there is a positive and strong correlation between a delegation of leaders and beneficiaries' involvement and success of the Girinka Program as Pearson correlation of .750** with p-value is 0.000, which is less than standard significance levels of 0.01. The results showed that there is a positive and very strong correlation between responsibility and accountability of leaders and success of Girinka program of Rweru and Gashora Sectors as Pearson correlation is .882 with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the standard significance level of 0.01. Overall findings on the correlation matrix show that there is a positive and very strong correlation between leadership management and success of Girinka program of Rweru and Gashora Sectors, Bugesera District, Rwanda as Pearson correlation is .982** with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the standard significance level of 0.01.

Introduction:

Rwanda is among the top ten countries in terms of improvements in GHI scores since 1990 (Grebmer et al., 2013). The Government of Rwanda has implemented many strategies in agriculture to increase food security such as agroforestry as one of the methods of controlling soil erosion by planting different types of trees that contribute as construction materials, livestock fodder, and food such as fruits and nuts which improve food security. Also, agroforestry provides biomass in the soil to improve soil fertility that increases agricultural production which results in increasing food security (the Republic of Rwanda, 2011).

Girinka (the "one cow per poor family" program) is encouraged as a strategy in Rwanda to reduce poverty, specifically where resource-poor farmers get a cow aimed at developing skills and accumulating assets for livelihood improvement as well as the promotion of improved soil fertility about manure use (Kim et al., 2013). More than 90% of Girinka beneficiaries use manure and attribute increased yields to enhance soil fertility which has resulted from the program. The Girinka program can be one of the adaptations as a climate resilience strategy for food security in Rwanda because it provides food such as milk, milk products (cheese, yogurt, butter), meat, and manure that is used to improve soil structure and rejuvenate tired land resulting in high crop production and food security (Send a Cow, 2008).

Despite the expected convenience of the Girinka Program to the poor people in Rwanda, there were different challenges faced during the implementation of this program, these are included by unprofessionalism dominant in the process of selecting people who may be given cows in the line of the Girinka program, non-participation of beneficiaries in decision making during the distribution of the cows, lack of capital for beneficiaries to support that cow to bring enough productivity; unavailability of veterinaries and lack of/or incomplete training and skills on how to manage their cows, no follow up of local leaders of Girinka program implementation, the death of some received cows, issue of water shortage and drought in some regions and insufficient land to grow forage for cows; inadequate training in managing manure use, and all these cause insufficiency of milk, meat and shortage of productivity from Girinka program for beneficiaries (David K.,

2014). It is therefore, this study was about the influence of leadership management on the success of the Girinka program in Rwanda especially in Bugesera District by replying to questions on which are mechanisms of leadership used by local leaders in Bugesera District; how is the success of Girinka program standing in Bugesera District; and how does leadership management influence the success of the Girinka program in Bugesera District.

Objectives of the Study:

This study generally assessed the influence of leadership management on the success of the Girinka program in Rwanda. While specific objectives are in four ways:

- To find out the influences of authority and follow up of leaders on success of Girinka program in Rweru and Gashora Sectors, Bugesera District
- To find out the influences of power and control of leaders on the success of the Girinka program in Rweru and Gashora Sectors, Bugesera District
- To evaluate the influences of delegation of leaders and beneficiaries' involvement on the success of the Girinka program in Rweru and Gashora Sectors, Bugesera District
- To analyze the influences of responsibility and accountability on the success of the Girinka program in Rweru and Gashora Sectors, Bugesera District

Review on Leadership Management:

According to Tuomi, (2002) management consists of controlling a group or a set of entities to accomplish a goal. Leadership refers to an individual's ability to influence, motivate, and enable others to contribute toward governmental success. Influence and inspiration separate leaders from managers, not power and control. Local leaders of successful authorities can easily relate to the Centre, while smaller authorities have less influence and credibility. Leadership is not only about charisma and individual qualities, but it is also about what leaders do and their approaches to change. There are numerous versions of leadership and misleading narratives about leaders in the press, but too little about their practice and understanding of how to deliver social change. Good leadership in the public sector depends on an ability to understand diverse perspectives and compose change in a manner that adds wider public value (Manning, N., 2005).

Components or/Mechanisms of Leadership Management:

According to Kuye and Mafunisa (2003:432), it is clear that leadership is a complex management activity. Particular components of leadership are authority, power, influence, delegation, responsibility, and accountability. Authority is the right of a leader to give orders and demand action from workers. Power, however, refers to the ability of a leader to apply authority in such a way that workers take action. At times the task of a leader might also be passing his/her authority to a subordinate to do something on his/her behalf. This entails subdividing a task and passing a part on to a worker with the necessary authority to execute it. The final part of leadership is accepting responsibility and accounting for it. To maintain effective leadership, one must save a delicate balance among the different leadership components (Thakhathi, 2000:78-79).

The Importance of Leadership and Governance:

Effective leaders lead their societies to greater heights of achievement, productivity, and ultimately prosperity if they are competent and inspiring leaders as well. It is in the public service that effective leadership is most needed. Effective managers are bearers of authority assigned to them by an organized structure that has the authority and right to organize to lead to the activities of others. Such an individual is a leader because has specific traits and a power base, consults his/her followers on particular matters, and motivates them to cooperate and to work according to their own free will (Kuye & Mafunisa, 2003:432).

Review on the Success of Girinka Program:

The Girinka (One Cow per Poor Family) program was initiated by HE President Paul Kagame in 2006 as part of the fight against rural poverty). The aim was to use livestock asset transfers to increase productivity in the livestock and agriculture sectors, and hence drive improvements in household incomes and reduce poverty among the rural poor (Ingabire, 2013; Argent et al. 2014). The major objectives of the Girinka Program include: reducing poverty through dairy cattle farming; improving livelihoods through increased milk consumption and income generation; improving agricultural productivity through the use of manure as fertilizer; and improving soil quality and reducing erosion through the planting of grasses and trees. The program also was intended to promote unity and reconciliation among Rwandans based on the cultural principle that if a cow is given from one person to another, it establishes trust and respect between the giver and the beneficiary (Hahirwa & Kalinganire, 2017).

Qualities/Traits Theory:

According to the theory of leadership traits, the leader is a particular type of person with particular capabilities; and his leadership is based on putting these characteristics or competencies into practice (Gumingham and Gephart, 1973:2). One of the earliest approaches for studying leadership was the trait approach. Generally, there is considerable variation in the personality, ability, capabilities, and skills of successful leaders. However, research reveals that some traits appear more consistently than others. It should be remembered that although the statistical correlations between these traits and leadership are positive, the

correlations are often low, and also do not prove the cause-and-effect relationship. It may require one set of traits to achieve a position of leadership and another set of abilities to maintain that position (Beach, 1985:335).

Empirical Studies Review:

Joseph Gumira H. & Charles K., (2017) exploring the success and challenges of the Girinka program and the need for social work involvement: Southern Province, Rwanda. The approach consists of providing a milk cow to poor households to ensure milk supply to children. The issued milk cows are not only for milk consumption but also for enabling beneficiaries to get out of poverty through selling surplus milk and using manure to increase land fertility for agricultural production. The objectives of this article are to understand how the Girinka program works, highlighting its success in empowering poor households and examining the challenges and obstructions it faces, and eventually emphasizing the role of social work in coping with them. The role of social work practitioners along with local public staff in charge of social services for instance be that of using strengths perspective to facilitate beneficiaries and potential beneficiaries of the program on the waiting list to find alternative solutions to their problems and build up their self-sufficiency through an empowerment approach. The Girinka program was set up with the central aim of reducing child malnutrition rates and increasing the household incomes of poor farmers. These goals are directly achieved through increased access to, and consumption of milk, by providing poor households with a heifer. The program is crucial to addressing the fundamental needs of those parts of the country that are critically food insecure. The Girinka program is transforming rural livelihoods and addressing poverty alleviation in Rwanda. The model is simple, the impact is great. One Cow brings nutrition, sustenance, and employment provides a stable income for a family and is a source of soil nutrients via manure to assist small scale (Heifer International program, 2007).

Conceptual Framework:

To resolve the problem of this research, this study established a relationship between independent variables in terms of leadership management and dependent variables in terms of the success of the Girinka Program as figure 1 displays below.

Research Design and Methodology:

The study used quantitative because the authority and follow up, power and control, responsibility and accountability in leadership management used by local leaders, and delegation of leaders and beneficiaries' involvement influenced the success of the Girinka program in Rweru and Gashora Sectors, Bugesera District. The study used a correlative design that shows the relationship between variables under study. Target population was 41 people in Rweru and Gashora Sectors, Bugesera District. Sampling technique was census used to fulfill

the missions required by the law, that is, a count of the population in Rweru and Gashora Sectors, Bugesera district, and its administrative constituencies by using universal sampling technique was used to select 41 of respondents as sample size. The purpose of the census was to get a broader sense of the population in general.

Questionnaires were distributed to beneficiaries and local leaders in two sectors in Bugesera District. SPSS IBM 22.0 version software was used to analyze the data obtained in this research. The descriptive statistical method was used to describe the frequency, percentages, and cumulative percentage of data collected from respondents. The coefficient of determination specifically the regression analysis model was applied to test the relationship between variables, the model equation is: $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \epsilon$

X is leadership management as the independent variable; while, y is the success of Girinka Program;

β_0 is constant number; β_1 - β_4 are coefficient of determinants;

X1: Authority and follow up of leaders;

X2: Power and control of leaders;

X3: Delegation of leaders and beneficiaries' involvement;

X4: Responsibility and accountability.

Analysis of Results and Discussions:

In this study, the correlation matrix shows a table presenting correlation coefficients between variables. Each cell in the table shows the correlation between two variables. A correlation matrix is used to summarize data, as input into a more advanced analysis, and as a diagnostic for advanced analyses. The findings on the correlation matrix test of this study between variables of leadership management as independent variable and Success of Girinka Program as the dependent variable are in table No1.

Table 1: Correlation Coefficient Matrix Results

		Authority and follow up of leaders	Power and control of leaders	Delegation of leaders and beneficiaries' involvement	Responsibility and accountability of leaders	Leadership management	The success of the Girinka Program
Authority and follow up of leaders	Pearson Correlation	1	.788**	.842**	.856**	.814**	.747**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N		41	41	41	41	41
Power and control of leaders	Pearson Correlation		1	.742**	.889**	.929**	.910**
	Sig. (2-tailed)			.000	.000	.000	.000
	N			41	41	41	41
Delegation of leaders and beneficiaries' involvement	Pearson Correlation			1	.735**	.795**	.750**
	Sig. (2-tailed)				.000	.000	.000
	N				41	41	41
Responsibility and accountability of leaders	Pearson Correlation				1	.938**	.882**
	Sig. (2-tailed)					.000	.000
	N					41	41
Leadership management	Pearson Correlation					1	.982**
	Sig. (2-tailed)						.000
	N						41
The success of the Girinka Program	Pearson Correlation						1
	Sig. (2-tailed)						
	N						

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Findings in table No1 show correlation coefficient matrix results where the results show that there is a positive and strong correlation between authority and follow up of leaders in leadership management and success of Girinka program as Pearson correlation is .747** with the p-value of 0.000, which is less than the standard significance level of 0.01. This specifies that out of the considered other factors influencing the success of the Girinka Program, only authority and follow-up of leaders in leadership management has a significant influence of 74.7% on the success of the Girinka program of Rweru and Gashora Sectors, Bugesera District, Rwanda. Once again, the results show that there is a positive and very strong correlation between power and control of leaders and success of the Girinka Program as Pearson correlation is .910** with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the standard significance level of 0.01, and this directs that, out of the considered other factors of leadership management, only the power, and control of leaders has a significant relationship of 91.0% with the success of Girinka program of Rweru and Gashora Sectors, Bugesera District, Rwanda. The results show that there is a positive and strong correlation between a delegation of leaders and beneficiaries' involvement and success of the Girinka Program as Pearson correlation of .750** with p-value is 0.000, which is less than standard significance levels of 0.01. This indicates that, out of the considered other factors of leadership

management influencing the success of the Girinka program, only delegation of leaders and beneficiaries' involvement has a significant relationship of 75.0% with the success of Girinka program of Rweru and Gashora Sectors, Bugesera District, Rwanda. The results show that there is a positive and very strong correlation between responsibility and accountability of leaders and success of Girinka program of Rweru and Gashora Sectors as Pearson correlation is .882 with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the standard significance level of 0.01. This indicates that, out of the considered other factors affecting the success of the Girinka program, only responsibility and accountability of leaders has a significant relationship of 88.2% on success of Girinka program of Rweru and Gashora Sectors, Bugesera District, Rwanda. Overall findings on the correlation matrix show that there is a positive and very strong correlation between leadership management and success of Girinka program of Rweru and Gashora Sectors, Bugesera District, Rwanda as Pearson correlation is .982** with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the standard significance level of 0.01. This indicates that, out of the considered other factors influencing the success of the Girinka program, leadership management has a significant relationship of 98.2% on success of the Girinka program of Rweru and Gashora Sectors, Bugesera District, Rwanda.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis:

Findings show the coefficient of determination specifically linear regression analysis model was applied to test the relationship between variables, the model equation is $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \epsilon$; where β_0 is constant; $\beta_1 - \beta_4$ are coefficient of determinants; x_1 : Authority and follow up of leaders; x_2 : Power and control of leaders; x_3 : Delegation of leaders and beneficiaries' involvement; x_4 : Responsibility and accountability. In this study, regression analysis helped to test null research hypotheses as detailed below.

Table 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.934 ^a	.873	.858	2.95855

a. Predictors: (Constant), Responsibility and accountability of leaders, Delegation of leaders and beneficiaries' involvement, Power and control of leaders, Authority and follow up of leaders

Findings in Table No2 present value of R. equals .934a while R-square of this study is .873 that means the percentage of influences on the success of the Girinka program in Bugesera District, Rwanda (as dependent variable) are explained by independent variable indicated by leadership management represented by responsibility and accountability of leaders, a delegation of leaders and beneficiaries' involvement, power and control of leaders, authority and follow up of leaders on the rate of 87.3%. This indicates that the model is positive and very strong, as the independent variable very highly explains the dependent variable (success of the Girinka program in Bugesera District). The adjusted R-square is used to compensate for additional variables in the model. In this case, the adjusted R-square is also 85.8%.

Table 3: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	2158.842	4	539.710	61.660	.000 ^b
	Residual	315.109	36	8.753		
	Total	2473.951	40			

a. Dependent Variable: Success of Girinka Program
 b. Predictors: (Constant), Responsibility and accountability of leaders, Delegation of leaders and beneficiaries' involvement, Power and control of leaders, Authority and follow up of leaders

Findings in ANOVA Table no3, level of fit mode is 61.660 with a p-value of 0.000b which is less than 0.01, set as the standard significance level. This means that null hypotheses including Ho1, Ho2, Ho3, and Ho4 stated that "There are no significant influences of authority and follow up used by local Government leaders on the success of Girinka program in Bugesera District; there are no significant influences of power and control of the leadership of local government leaders on the success of Girinka program in Bugesera District; there are no significant influences of delegation of leaders and beneficiaries' involvement on the success of Girinka program in Bugesera District, and there are no significant influences of responsibility and accountability in leadership used by local Government leaders on the success of Girinka program in Bugesera District"; they all are rejected because findings confirmed that independent variable influence significantly success of Girinka program in Bugesera District, Rwanda.

Table 4: Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	6.153	1.839		3.346	.002
	Authority and follow up of leaders	.789	.405	.283	1.949	.009
	Power and control of leaders	1.459	.375	.528	3.893	.000

Delegation of leaders and beneficiaries' involvement	.756	.346	.251	2.187	.003
Responsibility and accountability of leaders	1.347	.450	.470	2.993	.005
a. Dependent Variable: the success of Girinka program in Bugesera District					

$Y = \alpha + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \beta_4x_4 + \epsilon$ while Y is Dependent variable—the success of Girinka program in Bugesera District; $Y = 6.153 + .789x_1 + 1.459x_2 + .756x_3 + 1.347x_4 + 1.839$. The linear regression equation shows that the success of the Girinka program in Bugesera District will always depend on a constant factor of 6.153 regardless of the presence of other influences. The other variables explain that; every unit change in authority and follow up of leaders; power and control of leaders; delegation of leaders and beneficiaries' involvement; responsibility and accountability of leaders will significantly change the success of Girinka program in Bugesera District by .789; 1.459; .756; and 1.347 with standard error of 1.839.

Conclusion:

The program always intended to target the poor, subject to them having sufficient resources to care for the animal. This program should follow the steps on how the project is supposed to be managed. The program requires improving the styles of management like to increase training and skills related to breeding, participation of beneficiaries in decision making, and respect the suggestions given by the beneficiaries. The findings showed also that the production from the Girinka program is still insufficient which requires the top management to increase the strategies (an increase of budget, increase the number of expert veterinarians) of managing this program to bring the success of the program. Different types of training can focus on different aspects of these pathways. Providing the livestock with a suitable shed for example helps to secure and safeguard the animals by providing adequate space and protecting them from forces of nature, such as heat. Training on diseases similarly protects the animal's health. Improved health led to a higher likelihood of production which contributes to sustaining and increasing milk production. Improved feeding practices would further be expected to lead to better quality and a higher quantity of milk produced.

Recommendations:

To Bugesera District and other Government partners; the central Government should allow and facilitate in place the private veterinary service provider and agro-vets' inputs suppliers to have more milk increased for sell and home use, and disease cases in several areas will be reduced due to the private veterinarians that established in different corners of the sector. Local leaders should sensitize the dairy farmers to plant sufficient fodder for their cows, which can take them for the whole year. The Bugesera District should put in place clear rules and policies known by program implementers and beneficiaries that make them increase their knowledge about project management and the Girinka program success which led to sustainable development. Beneficiaries need education, sensitization, and mobilization because local people are ignorant, illiterate, and need more explanation about the problem to be solved. The livestock experts/ veterinarians should have continuous training to dairy farmers in general, for sufficient knowledge that could help them in achieving more.

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